
BODYinTRANSIT: Sensory-driven Body Transformation Experiences On-the-move

A Data Management Plan created using PGDOnline

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Funder: European Commission (H2020)

Template: Horizon 2020 DMP

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Project abstract:

Our physical body is the interface between ourselves and the world around us. The way we perceive our body, its appearance, configuration and motor abilities shapes our behaviour, emotion and social functioning. New sensor-based and bodily sensory feedback devices, such as those brought by immersive virtual reality, allow creating Body Transformation Experiences (BTE). These perceptual illusions, like being in a child's body, lead to experience changes in one's own body. Beyond fun experiences, the new field of BTE engineering brings a significant leap for wellbeing and health applications, as well as for the embodiment of robotic devices and virtual avatars, and smart clothing. However, the neuroscience of core sensory-driven changes in Mental Body Representations (MBR) currently represents piecemeal experiments in very controlled settings that restrict body movement. This hinders the transfer of the basic principles discovered to real-world complex environments and practical problems. Through systematic and iterative research, BODYinTRANSIT will establish a theoretical 'BTE design framework' for individualized sensorial manipulation of MBR with long-lasting effects in everyday use contexts. The framework will stand on four scientific pillars to induce, measure, support, personalize and preserve body transformations: 1) neuroscience of multisensory body perception, 2) data modelling of the links between MBR, behaviour, emotion and social functioning, 3) wearable-based embodied multisensory interaction design, and 4) field studies in real-life and on-the-move contexts with physically inactive users, somatic practitioners and users with body image concerns. Tangible outcomes will include design principles, data formats, models, measures and paradigms enabling and guiding BTE engineering innovations. BODYinTRANSIT envisions personalized BTE technologies able to measure MBR and adapt bodily sensory feedback to modify it - individually, online and while on-the-move.

Last modified: 22-02-2021

BODYinTRANSIT: Sensory-driven Body Transformation Experiences On-the-move - Initial DMP

1. Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

- State the purpose of the data collection/generation
- Explain the relation to the objectives of the project
- Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected
- Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)
- Specify the origin of the data
- State the expected size of the data (if known)
- Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

1. PURPOSE OF DATA COLLECTION

Research questions will be addressed through a combination of quantitative and qualitative human-computer interaction and neuroscience approaches. Studies will employ both within- and between-subjects designs involving research on humans. All of the data intended to be collected and analyzed in the course of the BODYinTRANSIT project are relevant, essential and required to achieve the objectives of the project. This is because:

- (1) We do not collect any data for which we do not have a specific hypothesis to test.
- (2) There are no prior existing datasets that could be used to address our hypotheses.
- (3) For each experiment, we have identified the necessary sample size for the number of participants needed as well as the amount of data needed to be collected from each participant.

2. RELATION TO THE PROJECT RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

There are 5 research objectives (RO) in the project:

RO1: To develop a theoretical framework integrating multidisciplinary research on mental-body representations (MBR) and guiding the design of future technologies for Body Transformation Experiences (BTE).

RO2: To identify, map and validate non-visual cue combinations – auditory, tactile, proprioceptive - and underlying top-down and bottom-up mechanisms that are the most effective for transforming MBR in terms of body appearance and body capabilities.

RO3: To understand and quantify the within- and between-subject inter-dependence of MBR with the variables of behaviour, emotion and self-identity, expanding BODYinTRANSIT forward model.

RO4: To investigate the short- and long-term effects in MBR malleability and persistence of the effects in complex environments, including longitudinal studies and field studies with representative populations (body image concerns, physically inactive, dancers).

RO5: To lay the knowledge basis for new technologies supporting the “inner fashion” concept which uses smart clothing to shape body perception, as validated in real-life studies.

These ROs will be achieved with a research program with 5 interconnected work packages (WPs).

- **WP1** will act as a focus point iteratively integrating project’s knowledge into a theoretical framework (**RO1**). WP1 does not involve data collection per se, but the project findings generated in the other WPs will be used in WP1.
- **WP2** will systematically map the most instrumental multisensory cues to **induce** alterations in MBR, both in perceived body appearance and in body capabilities by means of controlled laboratory studies (**RO2**). WP2 will also study the **preservation** of the effects with repeated exposure to the feedback and limits in MBR malleability (**RO4**).
- **WP3** will focus on **modelling** the data generated in WP2, to provide the individualized connection between changes in MBR, behaviour and emotion (**RO3**). WP3 does not involve data collection per se, but the modelling will be performed on the data generated in WP2 and WP5.
- **WP4** will employ a user-centred iterative design and optimization approach for the HW&SW development **supporting** the interactive BODYinTRANSIT gear prototypes tailored to users (**RO5**). It will involve work- shops and art-science residencies in the form of Embodied Design Explorations with stakeholders and inner fashion designers, fast prototyping techniques and user tests in real-life scenarios.
- **WP5** will involve field studies aimed to validate the principles, models and measures in real-life contexts for **personalization** of BTE technology and long-term effects (**RO4**). Three populations (dancers, inactive, eating disorders) will be tested to target a wide range of body perceptions. WP5 will address top-down influences of individual and context cues that will inform the BODYinTRANSIT model and the acceptability/feasibility of BTE technology in real-life.

3. TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA GENERATED/COLLECTED, ORIGIN AND EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

The BODYinTRANSIT dataset includes Behavioral, Psychophysiological and Survey measures from adult human participants in experiments, as well as audio/image recordings, diaries and drawings from participants. The types and formats, origin and expected size of the data are summarised in Table 1 below. The dataset will be filled out with subsets of data emerging from the

different experiments of the project.

Table 1: Types, origin, expected size and format of the data generated, as well as number of observations

Type of data	Origin (measures)	Expected size	Format	Number of observations
Survey data	-Participants personal and demographic information: Sex, Age, Body dimensions, Body weight, Professional Experience/Background -Health data: Eating disorder symptomatology, Physical activity habits	200 MB	.csv	600
Survey data	Participants' responses to psychological questionnaires on perceived body appearance/capabilities body satisfaction/concerns, body ideals, personality traits, self-concept in social groups, social stereotypes	200 MB	.csv	600
Behavioral	-Psychophysical data: Body perception tasks such as body visualization, estimates of body appearance/capabilities, localization of body landmarks. Computer-based implicit self-group association tests -Body movement/posture data: joint positions, cycle duration, angular velocity, acceleration, applied forces measured by sensors	2.5 GB	.csv	600
Psychophysiological data	Electromyography, Electrodermal activity, heart activity, respiration, measured by sensors	2.5 GB	.csv	500
Audio recordings	-Interviews about experiences and sensations during the experiments and embodied design explorations -Body interaction sounds during execution of physical activities	12.5 GB	.mp3, .wav	250
Image recordings	-Photographs and video recordings of participants performing the experimental tasks or embodied design explorations	500 GB	.jpeg, .tiff, .bmp, .mp4, .mov	500
Diaries	-Scans of paper diaries recording participants activities and sensations during field studies	200 MB	.pdf	100
Drawings	-Scans of body maps recording participants sensations in experiments	600 MB	.pdf	600

4. EXISTING DATA BEING RE-USED?: NO

5. DATA UTILITY: TO WHOM WILL IT BE USEFUL

2. FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- **Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)**
- **Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?**
- **Outline naming conventions used**
- **Outline the approach towards search keyword**
- **Outline the approach for clear versioning**
- **Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how**

Metadata will be used to make the dataset findable. Recorded metadata will include the following basic information:

- title of the dataset
- dataset persistent ID (DOI)
- author(s) (including ORCID and affiliation)
- publication date
- contact of the author(s) (email)
- description of the project
- description of the dataset
- description of the methodology used to generate the dataset
- subjects
- keywords
- language
- grant information
- depositor
- deposit date
- period of collection
- related publications
- privacy information

Making data openly accessible:

- **Specify which data will be made openly available. If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so**
- **Specify how the data will be made available**
- **Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data. Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**
- **Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited**
- **Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions**

The experimental raw data as the basis of the publication will be transferred to an open-science database and made accessible to interested colleagues worldwide. Pseudoanonymization is achieved by establishing no relation between the electronically stored experimental data and the personal data on the consent forms and the receipts for the participation fee. Personal data shared will include gender, age, body dimensions (e.g. body mass index, weight or height), possibly professional experience (dance and/or technological experience). Other personal data includes movement or peripheral physiological data, but only features extracted from the raw data (e.g. means, peaks) will be shared as open access. The pseudoanonymized raw movement or peripheral physiological data, and health-related data reflecting levels of physical activity and eating disorder symptomatology derived from a questionnaire will be made available to the scientific community for their exploitation under request.

The data will be deposited in the Institutional Repository of Universidad Carlos III de Madrid repository, e-Archivo (<https://e-archivo.uc3m.es/>) which is part of the E-ciencia Datos repository (<https://edatos.consorciomadrono.es/>). E-ciencia Datos is a multidisciplinary repository managed by a consortium of the main public universities of the Region of Madrid (Consortio Madroño). It offers all the services required by the project (storage and publication of datasets, assignation of DOI, standardized citations, long-term preservation, etc.). Furthermore, E-ciencia Datos Repository is OpenAIRE compliant

(https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataproviderdatasourceId=re3data____:d93c4a27c67bb01000f54df73035dbdc).

Pseudonymization versions of the survey data, behavioral experiments and psychophysiological measurements will be publicly available and mainly be useful for research purposes.

Metadata will be available online through the public repository. By publicizing basic information on the dataset (author, subjects, keywords...), metadata will help to make data discoverable. The following tools will help to spread the information on the availability of the data in the scientific community:

- project website
- search via repository
- data citations in publications
- websites of UC3M (<https://www.uc3m.es>)

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability

A codebook of the BODYinTRANSIT dataset will be included explaining the methodology used to collect the data, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, units of measurement and the format of the data. Additional metadata will be published in the repository. The data will be stored in .csv format (see Table 1 above).

A well-established file organization helps to make data identifiable and accessible for current and future users. It prevents misunderstandings, especially when several researchers work on the same data. Best practices for defining file organizations include: 1) the definition of the types of data; 2) the insertion of contextual information; 3) the use of meaningful categories for the directories; 4) the choice of a directory naming convention. For practical reasons, a hierarchical file system will be used for the project (for example: /[project]/[experiment]/[YYYYMMDD]).

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- **Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible**
- **Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed**
- **Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why**
- **Describe data quality assurance processes**
- **Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable**

The openly available data will be licensed under a Creative Commons 4.0 International License. Specifically, data is intended to be released with an Attribution License (CC-BY-NC 4.0). To view a copy of this license: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>

Data will be progressively deposited in the UC3M repository during the project lifetime. The data and the metadata will be made publicly available, without embargo period, once the original results based on the collected data have been published by the project researchers to ensure intellectual property.

3. Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

- **Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs**
- **Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project**
- **Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation**

Ana Tajadura-Jiménez is the contact person for data management issues in her role as Principal Investigator of the BODYinTRANSIT project. No additional staff costs have to be accounted for making the project data open access. Furthermore, due to the limited size of the data generated, no additional resources are needed for the preservation of the data.

While the project is ongoing, the data will be stored in a Google Drive repository (GSuite for Education available to UC3M). This premium file serving option meets the requirements for securing the research data. The folders that are shared in Google Drive are restricted in access to the UC3M personnel working on the project. Thus, access is password protected, requiring personal university account credentials. Google has no right or access to the data in this Drive as the data is fragmented in different geographic locations when saved.

Further, to ensure data safety, the data will be encrypted and secured with passwords. Backups will also be encrypted. Google

Drive Revision history tool will allow recovering files in case of incident.

The data files will be managed and stored in a secure environment (computer systems with passwords, firewall system, and malicious intruder protection). Access to digital files will be controlled with two-steps identification processes and password protection. In addition, the files with individual information will be stored separately from the experimental data which will be pseudonymized. The key to merge the name of the participants to the collected data will be kept under lock and key by the PI of the project at the University facilities. The publications will not give any information that allows an identification of participants. The data selected for preservation and sharing will be indefinitely stored in the repository "e-Archivo". "EArchivo" repository ensures long-term preservation since it is not time-limited. As a consequence, the database is intended to be preserved in perpetuity.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Data will be encrypted and password protected. Only members of the team directly working with the data ("need to know") will have authorisation to access the data. Even in the remote case of a possible data leak or server hack the data stolen will be fully encrypted and thus fully non accessible.

The recording and evaluation of the subject data is pseudonymized, and the longer-term storage is anonymized. The subjects' data and the behavioral and physiological data are encrypted so that only the project and the examiner remain recognizable. Each individual subject is assigned a number. Consent forms data are locked and stored separately from all further examination data. This way the assignment of the code number with the name of the subject would only be possible via the consent forms. The ids are assigned by the experimenter. Third parties will have no access to the consent forms. Consent forms will be destroyed once they are not necessary anymore for data treatment. As long as the consent forms exist, the test subject can request the deletion of all their data at any time. After annihilation of the consent forms, it is no longer possible to selectively delete records. We have conducted a Privacy Impact Assessment, which showed that the risk seriousness and likelihood given the planned or existing measures is negligible. These measures are summarised below.

Privacy risk management

An impact evaluation has been carried out together with the Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the Chief Information Security Officer (CISO) and the following measures to be applied are determined based on the types of data and treatments. This will be continuously reviewed if there are changes in the data treatment.

Storage and encryption

The consent of the participants will be scanned and encrypted with a tool similar to 7zip, and stored in digital hard disks on computers that are not connected to WAN Internet. Removable storage will be large capacity hard drives that will be kept in locked closets. To assure the participant's privacy, all experimental data will be pseudoanonymised, encrypted and stored on a cloud server (GSuite for Education) with server-side encryption and segmentation, and to which only the relevant staff have access. The hard drives of the personal computers used by the relevant staff will be encrypted at the operating system level. In the case of mobile devices, the device will be encrypted. Backup copies will be made weekly. Time machine or similar software will be used on an encrypted removable device.

Traceability

The cloud server (GSuite for Education) has an access log. The personal computers of the research team have an access record of the system itself; research team users will not be system administrators. For paper consent forms, a hard-copy (paper) access record will be kept.

Paper document security

The paper documentation containing the informed consents and the identifier of the pseudonymization will be kept under lock and key by the PI of the project at the University facilities. Exceptionally, questionnaires or pseudonymized surveys will be carried out on paper, which will be recorded in electronic format immediately after the experiment and will be destroyed subsequently.

Physical access control

Access to the office where the paper documentation is located is always closed and only the IP, cleaning staff and security personnel have access to it. Inside the office the documentation is kept in a locked cabinet, always closed and under the exclusive access control of the IP. Access control is carried out by the PI itself. The key will be guarded by the PI so that it is never available in the office.

Logical access control

The account for access to Google services will have two-step authentication activated. Personal computers will have their own accounts for each member of the project's research team. Mobile devices will have an access code (access fingerprint or code).

Malicious software reduction

The computers have the corporate anti-virus installed. Additionally, the perimeter firewall implements control measures to prevent the spread of malware.

Maintenance of personal computers

Personal computers come with a one-year manufacturer's warranty. After that year they will be repaired in case of problems.

Network security

The IT and communications service applies the security restrictions contained in the best practices. The computer and

communications service incident response team has a SIEM to detect possible intrusions and anomalies in network traffic, as well as potentially dangerous accesses.

Hardware security

When the personal computers are in the University facilities, they are in lockable offices with 24/7 security.

Protection against non-human sources of risk

The University has 24/7 security, there is a fire detection and protection system

Personnel management

The entire research team, including the IP, will receive 30-minute training from the DPO and the University CISO on the duty of confidentiality and compliance with the obligations derived from the privacy regulations.

Management of personal data breaches

In the event that an incident occurs that affects the fundamental rights of the interested parties, the DPO of the University will be communicated immediately by email to the address dpd@uc3m.es for their assessment, evaluation and decision-making in this regard.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

Ethical aspects to be evaluated are classified into two types:

1. Research on Humans

The research involves (1) non-invasive testing, using standard psychophysical and psychophysiological techniques and self-report, (2) the delivery of sensory feedback, and (3) the acquisition of peripheral physiological signals, such as heart rate, electrodermal activity, non-verbal expressions (facial, body movement/posture) and audiovisual recordings.

Participants taken part in the studies will be adults, able to give consent. The majority of experiments will recruit healthy subjects, except for a subset of the population tested who will be patients with Eating Disorders.

2. Protection of Personal Data

See Table 1 for summary of data to be collected

These aspects are covered in the Ethics Application submitted for assessment to the Research Ethics Committee of the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (the Host Institution) and to the ERC Ethics panel.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

BODYinTRANSIT will conform to relevant EU legislation such as:

- Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948)
- EU Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, Dec 2000 (specially Art. 3: right to the integrity of the person; and Art. 8: protection of personal data)
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)
- Treaty on the European Union (TEU): Article 6

BODYinTRANSIT will also conform to relevant National legislation such as:

- **Spain:** Ley Orgánica 15/1999, de 13 de diciembre, de Protección de Datos de Carácter Personal. A new Data Protection Act approved in July 2018 to align to EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR)

The procedures for BODYinTRANSIT data treatment has been registered and published at the UC3M record of activities of processing of personal data. They can be accessed following this link:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JqzBjNy2gVyPeOjGFgoxx9gTDMUEH6WO5HSqLNjh3R4/edit>